

Appraisal of elevated fluoride concentration in ground water using statistical correlation and regression study

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Abstract : In order to predict the suitability of water for different purposes viz. drinking, irrigation etc. and protect the environment determination of a large number of water parameters becomes evident. Statistical analysis has gained the popularity in overcoming such laborious and tedious operation. The water quality, with special reference to fluoride, of the area of Nalhati and Rampurhat block of the Birbhum district was assessed. Correlation between fluoride and other significant water quality parameters was made in order to find out their mutual dependence. It is found that an appreciable correlation holds for fluoride with pH, E.C., sodium, alkalinity, hardness and calcium and low correlation for fluoride with chloride, phosphate, iron and sulphate. Interestingly, fluoride is found to bear a positive correlation with pH and sodium while a negative correlation exists for fluoride with both potassium and alkalinity which is explained considering the local geological condition and mineralogical phase like secondary mineral depositions through weathering, companion ions, pH and properties of clay minerals.

Keywords : Fluoride, ground water, statistical analysis.

Fluoride rich groundwater ($>1.5 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$) has been found worldwide and also in various states in India including West Bengal¹. The fluorosis (fluoride related disease) symptoms include dental mottling, respiratory distress, stiffness in knees or elbows². Data regarding source of occurrence, speciation and health hazards are essential in the context of monitoring and management and hence for the safeguard of ecosystem.

The quality of water may be described according to their physicochemical and microbiological characteristics. A complete specification of water requires estimation of a large number of parameters. Moreover, for effective maintenance of water quality through appropriate control measures, continuous monitoring of quality parameters is essential. However, it is very difficult and laborious task for regular monitoring of all the parameters even if adequate manpower and laboratory facilities are available. An alternative approach may therefore be to establish some mathematical relationship between two individual parameters that are mutually and statistically correlated. Statistical correlation is effectively applied to multivariate complex geochemical data to reveal the underlying factors responsible for the observed variations in different parameters. The idea is based on that if good correlation exists between individual parameters then the deter-

mination of only few parameters sufficiently described the overall water quality. Thus, correlation has been used for³ : the assessment of overall water quality; the determination of range of variability of parameters to indicate extreme of quality; the prediction of validity of any particular removal technique in real samples.

An attempt has been made in the present investigation for a systematic calculation of correlation coefficient between each pair of water quality parameters in an aim to minimize the complexity and dimensionality of large set of data.

Results and discussion

The water samples collected from different sources are found to have different fluoride level. With respect to fluoride concentration 40% samples are found safe ($< 0.5 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$), 25% samples lie within maximum permissible level ($0.5\text{--}1.5 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$), 22.5% are moderately high ($1.5\text{--}3.5 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$), 2.5% samples are high ($>3.5 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$) while 10.0% samples are abnormally high ($7.0\text{--}19.0 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$). Fluoride concentration in the groundwater, as arises through geological route⁴, is found to have seasonal variation, probably due to evaporation and transpiration and water table fluctuation. The mean value for each parameter is, therefore, presented in the present case (Table 1). It is observed that fluoride con-

Table 1. Physico-chemical parameters of water samples

Sample no.	pH	E.C.	T.D.S.	F ⁻	Cl ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	T.H.	T.A.	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Ca ²⁺	Fe (Total)
1.	6.7	2946.00	1662.00	0.47	750.7	0.06	367.12	613.1	460.0	144.00	14.0	245.30	0.35
2.	7.5	680.60	394.30	1.20	136.1	0.02	22.60	83.19	260.0	70.00	49.00	33.27	0.40
3.	8.8	552.60	315.80	19.00	146.1	0.07	0.68	10.0	140.0	138.01	1.40	4.02	0.36
4.	9.2	690.01	352.00	15.08	135.0	0.05	22.90	25.0	95.0	110.02	2.43	6.00	0.49
5.	7.4	200.02	120.01	0.21	21.0	0.06	2.10	75.0	73.0	5.96	4.68	22.02	0.42
6.	7.3	649.60	371.10	1.71	45.8	0.06	19.86	55.2	340.0	90.00	4.02	22.09	0.52
7.	5.6	470.00	256.30	3.5	42.6	0.05	3.10	28.0	100.0	8.60	8.40	4.18	0.78
8.	7.7	1380.01	672.50	1.28	174.0	0.05	4.00	195.0	427.0	183.00	6.63	42.00	0.66
9.	7.2	350.00	179.60	0.34	32.0	0.05	1.70	135.0	183.0	14.00	0.78	36.00	1.00
10.	6.6	340.02	174.40	2.7	42.6	0.05	1.47	140.0	170.0	35.0	0.60	6.85	0.59

All the parameters except pH and E.C. are expressed in mg dm⁻³, E.C. in μ s at 25 °C.

E.C. : Electrical conductance, T.D.S. : Total Dissolved Solids, T.H. : Total Hardness, T.A. : Total Alkalinity.

Sample source : 1–5 Nalhati block; 6–10 Rampurhat block.

centration of tube well, deep tube well and khadan is higher compared to that of well and dug well.

The correlation between twelve different water quality parameters such as pH, E.C., T.D.S., fluoride, chloride, sulphate, phosphate, hardness, alkalinity, sodium, potassium, calcium and iron are made in Table 2. The Pearson correlation coefficient significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed) and at 0.05 level (2-tailed) is determined. The correlation parameter indicates an appreciable correlation for fluoride with pH, E.C., sodium, alkalinity, hardness and calcium and low correlation for fluoride with chloride, phosphate, iron and sulphate. It is interesting to note that fluoride bears a positive correlation with pH and sodium while a negative correlation exists for fluoride with both potassium and alkalinity.

The observation is similar with the water quality trend of Nagaon and Karbi Anglong districts in Assam as reported by Chakrabarty *et al.* but is in contrary to the report of Das *et al.*⁵, particularly for correlation pattern of fluoride with potassium and alkalinity. Such deviation in water quality characteristic arises due to difference in local geological condition. The interpretation of fluoride content in ground water is quite complex as several factors like companion ions, pH, complex formation and properties of clay minerals play important roles during weathering of fluoride containing minerals. It is shown that activity of fluoride in ground water is inversely proportional to the activity (a) of H⁺, i.e. a function of pH at constant HCO₃⁻ concentration⁶.

The release of fluoride in ground water occurs in al-

kaline medium and 90% of the fluoride tends to be insoluble or tightly bound to particles in soils⁷. The positive correlation of Na⁺ and fluoride indicates that sodium fluoride is the key mineral for the elevated concentration of fluoride in ground water. It is observed that fissures and fractured zones of hard rock have secondary mineral depositions in the veins and fluoride is connected with endogenetic processes. Potassium remains occluded in the mineralogical composition causing its negative correlation with fluoride. Alkalinity (TA) of water arises due to the presence of CO₃²⁻ and/or HCO₃⁻ ion. It is found that (Table 2) both Na⁺ and K⁺ has positive correlation with TA. But correlation parameter for K⁺-TA is higher than that of Na⁺-TA, indicating the predominance of KHCO₃/K₂CO₃ over NaHCO₃/Na₂CO₃ in the studied samples⁸. Thus, alkalinity, being predominantly due to potassium, bears a negative correlation with fluoride in the present situation. Similar to the other reports⁵ negative correlation of fluoride with Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺ and total hardness is observed with the present set of data. This is thought to be due to the solubility restriction of the precipitated salt of fluoride⁹.

Dependence between fluoride and other parameters is judged from 1 : 1 correlation. Figs. 1 and 2 represents the correlation curve, as well as the regression line between fluoride and some typical parameters viz. alkalinity, hardness, sodium and calcium. The best fit linear relationship, obtained from the regression equation, for different pair of parameters are indicated in the following equation (eq. (1)) :

Table 2. Evaluation of coefficient of multiple water quality parameters

	pH	E.C.	T.D.S.	F ⁻	Cl ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	T.H.	T.A.	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Ca ²⁺	Fe (Total)
pH	1.000												
	-												
E.C.	0.084	1.000											
	0.607	-											
T.D.S.	-0.087	0.995 ^b	1.000										
	0.593	0.000	-										
F ⁻	0.670 ^b	-0.179	-0.176	1.000									
	0.000	0.268	0.279	-									
Cl ⁻	-0.064	0.973 ^b	0.975 ^b	-0.076	1.000								
	0.693	0.000	0.000	0.641	-								
PO ₄ ³⁻	0.048	-0.109	-0.115	-0.077	-1.07	1.000							
	0.767	0.505	0.482	0.638	0.511	-							
SO ₄ ²⁻	-0.201	0.802 ^b	0.825 ^b	-0.179	0.826 ^b	-0.073	1.000						
	0.213	0.000	0.000	0.268	0.000	0.656	-						
T.H.	-0.181	0.931 ^b	0.912 ^b	-0.311	0.886 ^b	-0.053	0.665 ^b	1.000					
	0.263	0.000	0.000	0.050	0.000	0.744	0.000	-					
T.A.	-0.082	0.676 ^b	0.691 ^b	-0.367	0.673 ^b	-1.30	0.510 ^b	0.558 ^b	1.000				
	0.623	0.000	0.000	0.020	0.000	0.424	0.001	0.000	-				
Na ⁺	0.134	0.325 ^a	0.322 ^a	0.341 ^a	0.352 ^a	-0.150	0.329 ^a	-0.199	0.224	1.000			
	0.41	0.041	0.043	0.031	0.026	0.355	0.038	0.217	0.165	-			
K ⁺	-0.266	0.433 ^b	0.431 ^b	-0.204	0.429 ^b	-0.141	0.474 ^b	0.399 ^a	0.252	0.141	1.000		
	0.097	0.005	0.005	0.208	0.006	0.385	0.002	0.011	0.118	0.387	-		
Ca ²⁺	0.016	0.756 ^b	0.752 ^b	-0.065	0.756 ^b	0.069	0.658 ^b	0.748 ^b	0.393 ^a	0.314 ^a	0.470 ^b	1.000	
	0.924	0.000	-0.000	0.689	0.000	0.674	0.000	0.000	0.012	0.049	0.002	-	
Iron (total)	-0.109	-0.302	-0.315 ^a	-0.194	-0.361 ^a	0.109	-0.271	-0.213	-0.086	-0.153	-0.348 ^a	-0.292	1.000
	0.503	0.058	0.048	0.229	0.022	0.505	0.091	0.186	0.554	0.345	0.028	0.067	-

^aSignificant at 0.05 level (2-tailed); ^bSignificant at 0.01 level (2-tailed); Sample size = 40.

E.C. = Electrical Conductance; T.D.S. = Total Dissolved Solids; T.H. = Total Hardness; T.A. = Total Alkalinity.

$$Y = AX + B \quad (1)$$

where, *X* is the independent variable and *Y* is fluoride, the dependent variable. *A* and *B* are the characteristic constants for a particular pair; *R*² indicates the regression

coefficient. The constants and the *R*² value for fluoride with other parameters are presented in Table 3. The statistical correlation and regression parameters are evaluated using Statistica 4.2 computer programme.

Fig. 1 : 1 : 1 Correlation of fluoride vs T.H. and T.A.

Fig. 2 : 1 : 1 Correlation of fluoride vs Na⁺ and Ca²⁺.

Table 3. Evaluation of regression parameters of fluoride with other individual water quality parameters

Parameter	A	B	R ²
pH	3.8777	25.841	0.4485
EC	-0.0009	3.4729	0.0322
TDS	-0.0018	3.4741	0.0308
Cl ⁻	-0.0016	2.9225	0.0058
PO ₄ ³⁺	-2.9864	2.9277	0.0059
SO ₄ ²⁻	-0.0103	3.0133	0.0318
Hardness	-0.0042	3.7198	0.0971
Alkalinity	-0.0143	5.8696	0.1129
Na ⁺	0.036	0.4319	0.1825
K ⁺	-0.048	3.1891	0.0418
Ca ²⁺	-0.0024	2.8723	0.0047
Fe (total)	-4.0484	4.8826	0.0378

E.C. : Electrical Conductance, T.D.S. : Total Dissolved Solids,

T.H. : Total Hardness, T.A. : Total Alkalinity.

Materials and methods :

Sampling : Water samples were collected in PET bottles (500 cm³) from forty different sources viz. tube wells, dug wells and khadan throughout a period of five years with one month intervals. Samples were collected from different sources viz. well (2.5%), tube well (55%), deep tube well (12.5%), dug well (17.5%), pond (5%) and khadan (2.5%). Some tap water samples (5%) were also collected.

Methodology : All the chemicals used are of AnalaR grade. Deionized water was used for all experiments. Fluoride content was determined both spectrophotometrically (UV-Vis spectrophotometer : Model No. VIS 7200, Tehnocomp, China) at 535 nm using SPDANS [sodium 2-(p-sulphophenylazo)-1,8-dihydroxy-3,6-naphthalein-disulphate] and potentiometrically (Ion meter : Model No. 340/Ion-Set, WTW, Germany) using fluoride sensitive electrode. In both cases calibration were made with known standard NaF solution. Flame photometer (Model No. CL 361, Elico, India) was used for determination of metal ions like Na⁺, K⁺ and Ca²⁺. Spectrophotometric method was used for the determination of nitrate (at λ_{max} 220 and 275 nm) and phosphate by molybdenum blue (λ_{max} 690 nm). Chloride and sulphate were determined following argentometry and turbidimetry respectively. Total hardness was calculated from chelatometric titration using EDTA. All the determinations were made following standard methodology¹⁰. Alkalinity, pH, conductance and total dissolved solid were determined using Water Quality Analyzer (Model No. PE 136, Elico, India).

Theoretical basis for statistical analysis :

Correlation coefficient is used to determine the relationship between two variables X (independent) and Y (dependent)¹¹. For a set of n observations (X_i, Y_i) where i = 1, 2, 3, 4, ...n, the correlation coefficient r between X and Y is given by the relationship

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i Y_i / \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2 \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i^2}}$$

where, X_i = x_i - \bar{x} ; Y_i = y_i - \bar{y}

$$\text{and } X = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i / n; \text{ and } Y = \sum_{i=1}^n y_i / n$$

If the correlation coefficient r between two variables is sufficiently high the variables are said to be high correlated. A linear relationship of the form

$$Y = AX + B,$$

$$\text{where, } A = \left[\frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i y_i) - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \right]$$

and

$$B = y_i - Ax_i$$

can be obtained in such situations, where, A and B are the constants for a particular set of experiments and can be determined by fitting the experimental data to the above equation¹¹.

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